

Membrane Potential Studies of $S_2O_3^{2-}$, $S_2O_4^{2-}$ and HPO_4^{2-} Anions by using Hemin Collodian Membrane Electrodes in Aqueous Media

M. G. SHET* and D. R. PANDIT

Department of Chemistry, Bhavan's College, Bombay-400 058

Manuscript received 8 February 1993, revised 13 August 1993, accepted 30 September 1993

Membrane potentials of $S_2O_3^{2-}$, $S_2O_4^{2-}$ and HPO_4^{2-} anions were determined by using membrane electrodes¹⁻³ in respective electrolytes at molarity ratios 2, 3 and 4, by exchange of Cl^- ions of varying thickness. Lindenfeld² replaced electrovalently bound Cl^- ions of hemin with Br^- and I^- . The valid range of concentration has been ascertained using Nernst expression at $25 \pm 1^\circ$ within the experimental error of $\pm 2.8\%$.

Results of Discussion

Hemin collodian membrane electrodes prepared were exchanged with $S_2O_3^{2-}$, $S_2O_4^{2-}$ and HPO_4^{2-} of aqueous electrolytic solutions of $Na_2S_2O_3$, $Na_2S_2O_4$ and Na_2HPO_4 from the measurement of membrane potentials in the concentration range 1×10^{-3} to 45.0×10^{-3} and 1.0×10^{-3} to 64×10^{-3} M at molarity ratios 2, 3 and 4 respectively. The membrane potential values (Table 1) obtained were lower than the theoretical values due to comparatively lower concentration of the critical ions in the membrane at this stage of consequent decrease, transport number of the critical ion, which is unity at lower concentration of the outside solution. Similar lowering was also observed by Sollner³ in case of protamine collodian membrane and by Basu⁴ of resin membrane electrode. The membrane potentials recorded in the observed column are the mean of the two sets of measurements made by reversing the

concentration inside and outside the membrane electrode. The valid range of concentration for the meaningful application of Nernst expression applicable is 2.0×10^{-3} to 8.0×10^{-3} M for $Na_2S_2O_3$, 8.0×10^{-3} to 45×10^{-3} M for $Na_2S_2O_4$ and 2.0×10^{-3} to 45.0×10^{-3} M for Na_2HPO_4 with experimental error of 2.8% at temperature $25 \pm 1^\circ$.

Experimental

Hemin is an anion-exchanger. Hemin collodian membrane electrode⁵ of different thickness were prepared as reported earlier¹. Finely powdered hemin and collodian (1 : 4) were mixed, shaken for 4-5 h, pressed under hydraulic press and membrane electrodes of various thickness (0.42 to 0.50 mm) were prepared. The membrane electrodes after prolonged conditioning⁶ in the respective electrolytes, which showed zero or negligible asymmetric potential in case of solution of same concentration on two sides, were used in determination of membrane potentials. The membrane potentials were determined by using an Ajco potentiometer. The individual activities of the anions at varying concentration in aqueous solutions were obtained by graphical plotting⁷. The theoretical values were determined from the Nernst expression,

$$E = \frac{RT}{nF} \log \frac{a_2}{a_1}$$

TABLE 1—MEMBRANE POTENTIALS OF $S_2O_3^{2-}$, $S_2O_4^{2-}$ AND HPO_4^{2-} MEMBRANE ELECTRODES AT $25 \pm 1^\circ$

Sl. no.	Electrolyte	Film thickness	Molarity ratio	Anion activity $\times 10^{-3}$		Membrane potential (mV)			
				Inside	Outside	Obs.	Calcd.		
1.	$Na_2S_2O_3$	0.42	2 : 1	01.93	00.98	08.60	08.77		
				03.80	01.93	08.52	08.71		
				04.50	03.80	08.52	08.65		
				27.96	14.52	—	08.41		
				53.37	27.96	07.40	08.30		
				0.46	3 : 1	02.86	00.98	13.75	13.84
						08.36	02.86	—	13.76
						13.65	04.73	13.50	13.65
						26.34	09.24	13.05	13.43
		38.61	13.65			13.10	13.36		
		03.80	00.98			17.35	17.48		
		0.48	4 : 1	07.45	01.93	17.20	17.37		
				14.52	03.80	—	17.23		
				27.96	07.45	16.60	17.00		
				53.37	14.52	16.55	16.69		
				0.46	2 : 1	01.93	00.96	08.46	08.77
						03.80	01.93	—	08.71
						07.45	03.80	08.25	08.65
0.48	3 : 1			27.96	14.52	07.95	08.41		
				53.37	27.96	07.30	08.30		
		02.86	00.98	13.60	13.84				
		08.36	02.86	13.45	13.76				
		13.65	04.73	—	13.66				
		26.34	09.24	13.25	13.43				
		38.61	13.65	12.65	13.36				
		0.48	4 : 1	03.80	00.97	17.25	17.48		
				07.45	01.93	—	17.37		
14.52	03.80			16.95	17.23				
0.48	2 : 1	27.96	07.45	16.70	17.00				
		53.37	14.52	16.10	16.69				
		01.93	00.98	08.35	08.77				
		03.80	01.93	08.25	08.71				
		07.45	03.80	08.15	08.65				
		27.96	14.52	07.85	08.41				
		53.37	27.96	07.05	08.30				
		0.43	3 : 1	02.86	00.98	13.50	13.84		
				08.39	02.86	—	13.76		
				13.65	04.73	13.25	13.66		
				26.34	09.24	13.05	13.43		
				38.61	13.65	12.55	13.36		
03.80	00.98			17.20	17.48				
0.45	4 : 1	07.45	01.93	17.00	17.37				
		14.52	03.80	16.80	17.23				
		27.96	07.45	—	17.00				
		53.37	14.52	16.00	16.69				

NOTE

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